

Saxa loquuntur: Understanding ordinary people through the tales of stones

JELENA VUKOJEVIĆ

PhD Candidate, University of Belgrade

Abstract

Our knowledge of ancient history and classical antiquity, in general, depends largely on the accuracy and soundness of documentary evidence. The importance of epigraphic sources for our knowledge of the ancient world is undeniable. Inscriptions represent an essential primary source that stands before us as inscribed thousands of years ago. They contain thoughts that have not been distorted by copying errors and misinterpretations typically associated with manuscript transmission. A valuable resource for historians, archaeologists, and other fields of research, inscriptions provide data on a wide range of topics, including the history and organisation of the vast Roman Empire, laws, administration, religion, emperors, military, socioeconomic relations, and so on. However, epigraphy also provides insight into the lives of ordinary people and gives voice to those who have been brushed aside throughout history. Communities, families, and individuals who do not play a major role in politics or social upheaval, who care for their families and loved ones, who worship gods or a god, who experience loss and death, and who fulfil their duties, come alive before us thanks to epigraphic material. The purpose of this essay is to demonstrate the ways in which epigraphic corpora can enrich our understanding of the daily lives of people whose actions have left no lasting impression on the pages of history. We should take the opportunity to gain insight into their family dynamics, their views on family, religion, and duty. The stones also bring out their views on death, loss, and love, which make them seem not so distant. Loyal colleagues and friends, dutiful soldiers and citizens, grieving parents and loving spouses speak to us through inscriptions from all corners of the Roman Empire.

Keywords: Epigraphic Sources – Latin Inscriptions – Ordinary People – Grief and Loss – Microhistorical Perspective

Introduction

Numerous scholars emphasise the profound significance of ancient inscriptions as invaluable historical artefacts. Latin inscriptions, in particular, are unparalleled reservoirs of information concerning ancient Rome, a fact widely acknowledged within scholarly circles.⁶⁰⁵ They offer insights into various facets of Roman society, including social, vocational, familial, and religious dimensions. These inscriptions grant us a unique perspective into the microcosms of families, social circles, and smaller communities within the Roman Empire, shedding light on the lives of ordinary citizens.

Scholars increasingly use inscriptions to illuminate overlooked aspects of antiquity, particularly the lives of Roman women. Hemelrijk's comprehensive work is notable for consolidating inscriptions from Latin-speaking provinces, supported by illustrative examples culled from the sources pertinent to each of the findings.⁶⁰⁶ Similarly, the collection "Women's Lives, Women's Voices" is a successful interdisciplinary study, integrating inscriptions with visual and archaeological evidence from Pompeii and Herculaneum.⁶⁰⁷

Analysing inscriptions from specific provinces, municipalities, or cities, whether extensive or limited, offers a unique opportunity. It allows for a detailed examination, providing a comprehensive view of seemingly inconspicuous segments of the Empire. The following analysis adopts a microhistorical approach, delving into the daily lives of ordinary citizens within a developing Roman settlement. This challenges conventional historical perspectives that prioritise major political events and figures. It is posited that a thorough exploration of specific locales lays a robust foundation for a nuanced history of everyday life. By gathering comprehensive data from a single location, this approach fosters greater confidence in our findings, in that it allows us to scrutinise the societal roles, interpersonal dynamics, and values of its inhabitants, drawing insights directly from the records and remnants left behind by the very individuals whose lives we seek to illuminate. This stands in stark contrast to approaches reliant on generalisations drawn from selectively chosen materials across regions, where conclusions are often filtered through the historian's lens, taking into primary consideration the implications of such data on major historical events.

⁶⁰⁵ "The value of inscriptions as historical material is immense. They are contemporary and authoritative documents, whose text is a first-hand record- ... They are the most important single source for the history and organisation of the Roman Empire; and their cumulative and comparative value ... is astonishingly great." R. G. Collingwood and Ian Richmond, *The Archaeology of Roman Britain* (London: Methuen & Co. Ltd, 1969), 193.

⁶⁰⁶ Emily A. Hemelrijk, *Women and Society in the Roman World: A Sourcebook of Inscriptions from the Roman West* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020).

⁶⁰⁷ Brenda Longfellow and Molly Swetnam-Burland, eds. *Women's Lives, Women's Voices: Roman Material Culture and Female Agency in the Bay of Naples* (Austin: University of Texas Press, 2021).

This research also places a crucial emphasis on studying emotions due to their potential influence on individuals' behaviour, choices, and interactions. By employing the framework of the history of emotions, historians aim to explore how societies perceived and valued emotions in specific historical periods, tracking the evolution of these concepts over time. This essay specifically delves into understanding how societal norms, religious beliefs, and political events impacted the emotional experiences of individuals or communities, with a particular focus on instances of love and grief. In this approach, the scarcity of reference material presents a common challenge, especially when dealing with marginalised subjects who left limited traces or documents detailing their lives and experiences. Despite this, epigraphic material as a primary source proves valuable, as it primarily provides unaltered information. The subjects provide insights in their own words, forming a direct dialogue with the researcher, even when mediated by a third party, like a stonemason shaping their thoughts.

This essay delves into a limited corpus of inscriptions from Sirmium, situated in Lower Pannonia. Due to its historical importance in the late Roman Empire, ample information about its public affairs is accessible. This makes it an apt subject for our examination, which extends beyond mere historical data. Despite its modest size, this corpus holds significance, enriching existing datasets and offering a nuanced portrayal of Sirmium's multifaceted existence.

Moving beyond traditional perspectives, a detailed examination of limited epigraphic corpora unveils insights into religious institutions, customs, and the reciprocal influence of new and old cultures, including potential syncretism between paganism and Christianity. This method confirms instances of laws and administrative regulations, providing a nuanced understanding of the balance between magistrates' formal duties and private lives. Funerary inscriptions also reveal family structures, allowing a focus on individuals' intricacies. Through a comparative study, we confirm the social and cultural development of a specific place, going beyond individual dynamics and challenges. This approach, inclusive of religious practices and cultural phenomena, prevents oversight during a focus on significant historical moments. At the core of this exploration is the individual, and examining how they navigated professions, communities, religions, and families is crucial. While the traditional approach, which prioritises onomastic and prosopographical analysis of inscriptions to extract historical evidence for reconstructing political, social, and economic aspects of ancient societies, has deepened our understanding of major changes, a novel perspective offers insights into the personal experiences of those impacted by them.

In this essay, I will rely primarily on funerary inscriptions. These form the majority of surviving inscriptions and yield extensive details about the dedicator(s) and honorand(s). Epitaphs reveal identities, family ties, occupations, social backgrounds, and ages at the time of passing. They

also commemorate relationships with friends, heirs, and patrons. Funerary monuments sometimes include depictions of the deceased and individuals with whom they shared significant bonds, thereby embedding the individual within a well-defined social and cultural milieu.⁶⁰⁸ While some inscriptions may be embellished for self-glorification, many sought to memorialise cherished family members and close associates. This sentiment extended beyond those in public life. The ostentatious tombs in prominent locations, once common, gradually diminished, especially in late antiquity. So much so that references to the tomb's commissioners eventually vanished.⁶⁰⁹

Sirmium

Sirmium, located on the marshy banks of the Sava River, held strategic advantages behind the Danubian *limes*. It was integrated into the Roman realm between 13 and 9 BCE under Octavian Augustus. Swiftly gaining military importance, Sirmium attained colonial status following the conclusion of the Domitian Wars along the Pannonian border.⁶¹⁰ Its peak came in the latter half of the third century, during a period of heightened frontier threats. Sirmium served as a vital hub for imperial activities, including troop gatherings, supreme command, imperial residence, and ceremonies.⁶¹¹ It gained the status of an imperial city and became the administrative centre for the province of Second Pannonia during the Tetrarchy, eventually extending its jurisdiction to the Illyric Prefecture.⁶¹² Its status as a significant Christian centre in the fourth and fifth centuries is also noteworthy.

Despite extensive excavations, only a fraction of Sirmium's history is known. Roman and Italian settlers, along with native Latin speakers, were present from the first century CE,⁶¹³ indicating the widespread adoption of the Latin language and culture. The embrace of Latin often coincided with adopting epigraphic practices, resulting in a valuable source of information. The Sirmium inscription corpus, comprising approximately three hundred inscriptions, varies in preservation, stone quality, length, dating, and typology.⁶¹⁴ Inscriptions are predominantly characterised as private in nature. As anticipated, a substantial portion of the corpus is constituted

⁶⁰⁸ Maureen Carroll, "Memoria and Damnatio Memoriae: Preserving and Erasing Identities in Roman Funerary Commemoration," in *Living through the Dead: Burial and Commemoration in the Classical World*, eds. M. Carroll and J. Rempel (Oxford: Oxbow Books, 2011), 65.

⁶⁰⁹ Jean-Marie Lassère, *Manuel d'épigraphie romaine I-II*, (Paris: Picard, 2005), I 238.

⁶¹⁰ András Mócsy, *Pannonia and Upper Moesia (Routledge Revivals): A History of the Middle Danube Provinces of the Roman Empire* (London: Routledge 2014), 112–113.

⁶¹¹ Miroslava Mirković, *Sirmium: its history from the First century AD to 582 AD* (Novi Sad: Faculty of Philosophy, Department of History, Centre for Historical Research, 2017), 11–12.

⁶¹² Mirković, *Sirmium*, 79.

⁶¹³ Mirković, *Sirmium*, 22.

⁶¹⁴ For further insights into the epigraphic habit, refer to Ramsay MacMullen, "The Epigraphic Habit in the Roman Empire," *The American Journal of Philology* 103, no. 3 (1982): 233–46.

by votive and funerary inscriptions, with a notable inclusion of nearly a third being Christian inscriptions.

Votive inscriptions manifest a dedicated focus on venerating the Capitoline triad, Mars, Neptune (a predictable homage considering the city's geographical context), and Mithras. A noteworthy observation is the prevalence of inscriptions and monuments commissioned by city magistrates (such as *beneficiarii consulares* and *decuriones*). In addition to these, the corpus includes numerous military inscriptions, those dedicated to the emperor's well-being, and a few milestones. Turning to the realm of funerary inscriptions, they come in various forms, composed and commissioned by individuals from diverse social, economic and educational backgrounds, primarily for family members. Notably, a limited number of epitaphs feature fragments of funerary poetry and verses in metre, adding a literary dimension to the corpus.

The majority of inscriptions are preserved inscriptions are in Latin, ranging from the first to the fifth century, with fewer fragmentary Greek inscriptions from the fourth century onward. Therefore, this paper will focus exclusively on the Latin inscriptions in this corpus.⁶¹⁵ Among them, a few inscriptions were selected. These, in relatively concise passages, provide details about the deceased and their lives while also hinting at specific social or religious implications. These include different social strata, the representation of the Christian community, its members, organisational aspects, the operation of legal inheritance rights, military careers, and similar themes. In briefer discussions, intriguing individual stories will be presented. Even without delving into socio-political, cultural, and other implications, these stories would significantly enhance the portrayal of the city's life.

⁶¹⁵ All inscriptions in the paper will be transcribed following the Leiden guidelines.

Artemidora

*Ego Artemidora feci viva me memori am ad dom(i)num | Synerotem int{e} | rantem ad dexte | ram inter Fortuna | ta{ne}m et d<e=I>siderium.*⁶¹⁶

While still alive, I, Artemidora, set up this monument in the basilica of master Syneros. It is located on the right side upon entering, situated between Fortunata and Desiderium.⁶¹⁷

Let us begin by examining a Christian funerary inscription in white marble, commissioned by a certain Artemidora for herself while she was still alive, within the Basilica of St. Syneros. This monument, taking the form of a plaque with meticulously arranged text and embellished with pilasters, can be traced back to the fourth or fifth century. From this inscription, we discern Artemidora's profound commitment to Christianity, as she ensured her resting place well in advance. Beyond manifesting her religious fervour, her final sepulchre bespeaks her elevated standing. Interment within a basilica, especially one housing the tomb of a Christian martyr (in this instance, Syneros), denoted a privilege granted to certain Christians in contrast to those interred outside the basilica, as such a space required purchase.⁶¹⁸

Basilicas functioned as collective commemorative structures; they were not designed to accommodate individual households or families but rather members of the same church community. Thus, through this inscription, Artemidora distinctly designates the location of her mortal remains (between Fortunatus and Desiderius). Yet, this detail does not primarily aim to distinguish and honour her as an individual. Instead, it underscores her integration into the Christian community of Sirmium and its collective identity. Consequently, a single sentence from the inscription vividly portrays an esteemed member of the local Christian community, who garnered ample influence and resources to be interred near a significant Christian martyr. Although she did not specify the precise span of her life, the fact that she secured a burial place for herself even during her lifetime suggests a lifespan of at least thirty years, characterised by devoted participation in church rituals and a prosperous occupation, potentially belonging to either her or members of her household.

⁶¹⁶ CIL III 10233 = ILCV 218.

⁶¹⁷ If not otherwise indicated, all translations are mine.

⁶¹⁸ Ann Marie Yasin, "Funerary Monuments and Collective Identity: From Roman Family to Christian Community," *The Art Bulletin* 87, no. 3 (2005): 446.

Christiani parvuli

*Hic duo innocentes | quiescunt Petrus et | Victorinianus fideles vixit Petrus an(no) uno | mense(m) dies VIII
Victori|nianus vixit an(nos) IIII m(enses) VII | dies XV.*⁶¹⁹

Resting here are two innocent and faithful souls, Petrus and Marcus. Petrus lived for 1 year, 1 month, and 8 days, while Victorinianus lived for 4 years, 7 months, and 15 days.

A modest rectangular marble slab unveils the profound tragedy of the premature demise of two young boys and the grief-stricken parents they left behind, evidently a single family. This epitaph commemorates Petrus, who graced the world for just over a year, and Victorinianus, who never reached his fifth year. The precise enumerating of the days lived by Petrus and Victorinianus shows how much parents cherished moments spent with them. The poignant phrase "*duo innocentes*" encapsulates the immense anguish of this loss.

Some scholars may interpret endearments on inscriptions merely as standardised expressions, rather than authentic indicators of familial sentiments.⁶²⁰ To bolster this view, adjectives denoting affection and commendation for the departed's virtues and character are recurring formulas on both pagan and Christian inscriptions. Nevertheless, this observation may also suggest a shared set of values between the two social communities. Despite the potentially formulaic nature of certain epithets (such as those emphasising the child's endearing, gentle, and innocent disposition), it is entirely possible that they were purposefully selected by grieving families as fitting characterisations of their departed loved ones.⁶²¹ Regardless of the variance in scholarly perspectives, it appears incontrovertible that the human experience remains profoundly unaltered by established customs. Even in cases where feelings might not have found expression in more original phrases, we can surmise the anguish experienced by parents tasked with burying a child, let alone two.

This inscription also attests that the two boys received baptism and were part of the Christian community (*fideles*). This detail may be accentuated due to the rarity of baptising children at such a tender age in early Christianity. By assuming they were baptised shortly after birth, we may also infer that their parents, too, likely received this sacrament, signifying their commitment to Christian practices. Furthermore, it suggests that the intolerance towards Christians, which endured in the distant past, diminished, and that Sirmium housed at least one Christian temple, separate from the necropolis.

⁶¹⁹ AE 2016, 1286.

⁶²⁰ Jonathan Edmondson, "Roman Family History," in *The Oxford Handbook of Roman Epigraphy*, ed. Christer Bruun and Jonathan Edmondson (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014), 571.

⁶²¹ Leonard A. Curchin, "Convention or Originality?: The Attributes of Christian Children in Latin Epigraphy," *Antigüedad y Cristianismo* 39 (2022): 71.

Distinguished soldier

*T(itus) Cominius | T(iti) f(ilius) Volt(inia) Seve|rus Vienna |(centurio) | leg(ionis) II Adiutric(is) | donis donat(us) | ab Imp(eratore) Caesare | Aug(usto) bello Dacico | torquibus armillis | phaleris corona val|lari vixit ann(os) XXXXV | T(itus) Caesernius Macedo | proc(urator) Aug(usti) her(es) ex test(amento) p(osuit).*⁶²²

T. Cominius Severus, son of Titus, hailing from the city of Vienne and affiliated with the Voltinia tribe, served as a centurion in the Second Legion – Adiutrix. During the Dacian war, he was presented with awards by Emperor Caesar Augustus, including torques, armbands, phalerae, and a camp crown. He lived for 45 years. His heir T. Caesernius Macedo, who held the position of procurator Augusti, had this made as stipulated in his will.

Upon a lavishly adorned marble altar-shaped monument, an illustrious career is inscribed. Titus Cominius Severus holds official Roman citizenship with voting privileges and is affiliated with the rural tribe *Voltinia*. This traces his origins back to Narbonese Gaul, and his birthplace, the city of Vienne on the eastern bank of the Rhone, is meticulously specified. From this city, Cominius embarked on a military trajectory that culminated in notable achievements. Attaining the rank of centurion, he exhibited exceptional military skills. His pinnacle exploits unfolded in the Dacian War, where he garnered four military accolades (*torques, armilla, phalerae, corona vallaris*). These commendations bear witness to his proficiency and audacity as he led charges against adversaries—a distinction personally acknowledged by Emperor Domitian.⁶²³

Given that his funerary inscription was raised in Sirmium prior to the end of his military service, it is conceivable that Cominius was stationed in the city, poised to lead a legion in forthcoming campaigns. While the circumstances of his demise elude us, it is evident that Cominius accrued substantial esteem in Sirmium during times of tranquillity. Furthermore, a camaraderie blossomed between him and the procurator Augusti—a high-ranking financial official reporting directly to the emperor—whom he designated as his successor. The inscription attests to Macedo's dutiful execution of his role, and the craftsmanship of the entire monument to Cominius' possession of considerable material assets, which in all likelihood also transitioned to the procurator. This camaraderie might not have developed had Sirmium not been the host to numerous garrisons over the years.

⁶²² CIL III 10224.

⁶²³ However, his name remains unmentioned on the monument. Given the allusion to the conflict with the Dacians and the dating to the first century, it is presumed that the dedicator deliberately excluded Domitian's name as a result of *damnatio memoriae*.

Character studies

The aforementioned inscriptions were deliberately chosen because, despite their relatively sparse texts, they contain significant implications regarding both the religious and socio-administrative milieu, in addition to providing insights into the lives of the deceased. It is worth noting that there are also inscriptions offering brief but illuminating glimpses into the characters and experiences of ordinary individuals. Within this narrative, selected life stories and personalities will be presented in a succinct manner, allowing for further exploration. In the following, the content of individual inscriptions will be presented more concisely, with a focus not on extracting details about socio-political structures, military, and other institutions. This is not due to a lack of such information, but rather because the research aims to set aside the broader aspects of society and instead concentrate on the individual destinies often disregarded by historiographic trends. Whether these inscriptions describe an entire life or just a specific detail, they contain enough interesting data to vividly depict the streets of Sirmium.

Among them, we encounter Maximina, whose final days were spent in Sirmium, alongside her husband who, on the tombstone, eloquently emphasised not only his love for her but also the profound attachment Maximina held for her homeland (Dalmatia).⁶²⁴ In a similar vein, Macedonius expressed profound admiration for his wife by referring to her as “*matrona*,” a testament to how she embodied feminine virtues like chastity, loyalty, and piety. Moreover, he acknowledged her adherence to Christian values and principles, underscoring her esteemed status within the Christian community. Moreover, this same inscription provides invaluable insight into the inauguration of a new basilica in the city, dedicated to the Sirmian martyr Ireneus.⁶²⁵ The modest sarcophagus narrative poignantly illustrates how, amidst profound sorrow, it succeeded in eternally reuniting a mother with her prematurely departed infant in a tender embrace.⁶²⁶

Likewise, we encounter two soldiers of the *clavicularii*, who collaborated in military service and shared the battlefield. Their respective wives, grappling with the profound pain of losing their husbands in battle, resolved not only to collectively bear the weight of grief but also to share the

⁶²⁴ CIL III 6441: *D(is) M(anibus) Maximina annos vixit | XXVII Gorgonius memori | am posuit compari su(a)e | carissim(a)e de provincia | Dalmatia defuncta penus | colonia(m) Sirmi(um) Manibus | posita memoria.*

To the spirits of the dead. Maximina lived for 27 years. Gorgonius erected this monument in loving memory of his dearest wife, originally from the province of Dalmatia, who passed away within the colony of Sirmium. Monument set up for the spirits of the dead.

⁶²⁵ Mirković 2017, no. 223: *In basilica domini n | ostri Erenei(!) (h)a(n)c(?) mem/oriam posuit Maced | onius una cum m | atrona{m} sua{m} M | ammete Zevenati.*

Macedonius, along with his lady wife Mammete Zevenati, erected this monument in the basilica of our master Ireneus.

⁶²⁶ CIL III 10215 = ILCV 3634: *In hanc arcam posita est | Aurelia Macrina quae | vixit annos XXXV et | Aurelius Iustinianus | <f=E>ilius pius qui vixit annum | unum et menses quinque.*

In this coffin lies Aurelia Macrina, who lived for 35 years, and Aurelius Iustinianus, a beloved son who lived for 1 year and 5 months.

financial burden of raising the monument.⁶²⁷ A young man of modest origins harboured a fervent passion for acquiring knowledge, eagerly embracing new insights. His trajectory towards a promising career in civil service was tragically truncated by an untimely demise.⁶²⁸

In the era preceding the widespread adoption of Christianity, citizens of Sirmium dutifully fulfilled vows to the Capitoline triad, Mars, and Neptune. These entreaties sought blessings not only for their loved ones but also for the welfare of the city itself, and, by extension, the reigning emperors. Additionally, evidence exists attesting to the prominence of the cult of the god Mithras, substantiated by a plethora of votive altars dedicated to him. Notably, this deity commanded his own temple within the city, a structure that also underwent extensive renovations.⁶²⁹ The diverse cultural tapestry of the city is further expressed the interment of an exorcist within its precincts.⁶³⁰

Conclusion

The analyses provided underscore the importance of delving deeper into inscriptions, going beyond their role as political and historical records. Exploring the lives of individuals with minimal historical footprints, whose experiences closely resonate with our own, offers a distinctive perspective. These inscriptions connect us with narratives and emotions, reflecting contemporary sentiments. Territories once under the Roman Empire host myriad small corpora, along with isolated inscriptions. The individuals, whether deceased or dedicants, need not remain in anonymity. Within these engraved words, the humanities discover fertile ground for exploration, extending beyond the immediate subject matter.

The vibrant tableau in Sirmium portrays an organised Christian community thriving alongside its pagan counterpart. Prosperous women commemorate themselves through monuments, exuding confidence in their faith, and finding eternal repose within the church. The

⁶²⁷ IJug 271: *D(is) M(anibus) | Ael(io) Ingen{uo} clav|iculario ex officio | pr(a)esid<i=E>s deci(dit) in bel(lo) | Aelia Procella con|iugi karissimo me/moria(m) posuit | Septi(mio) Decorato | claviculario ex officio | pr(a)esid<i=E>s deci(dit) in b<e=l>l(o) | Aelia Basilissa coniugi | karissimo memoria(m) | posuit.*

To the spirits of the dead. Aelia Procella erected a monument in memory of her dearest husband, Aelius Ingenuus, a key-keeper in the governor's office, who perished in war. Aelia Basilissa erected a monument in memory of her dearest husband Septimius Decoratus, a key-keeper in the governor's office, who perished in war.

⁶²⁸ CIL III 03240: *P(ublio) Ael(io) Respecto eq(uiti) R(omano) | a milit(iis) filio piissimo | et studiis omni praedito | P(ublius) Ael(ius) Trophimianus pater | v(ir) e(gregius) posuit.*

To Publius Aelius Respectus, a beloved son of equestrian rank who pursued a military career and excelled in all his endeavours, this monument is dedicated by his esteemed father, Publius Aelius Trophimianus.

⁶²⁹ AE 2016, 1279: *Deo Soli In|victo Mi|t<hr=RH>ae C(aius) Iul(ius) | Italicus dec(urio) | col(oniae) Sirme(n)s|ium templum | vetustate | conlabent|<em=A> restituit a | solo.*

C. Iulius Italicus, a decurion of the colony Sirmium, restored a temple dedicated to the invincible sun god Mithra, rebuilding it from the very foundation due to age-induced deterioration.

⁶³⁰ AE 1996, 1256: *In hoc l[oco] | iacet Urs[ici]n[us] exorcist[a] | co<m=N>memorati[one(m)] | fecit Laurentia | [sa]nctimonia[li]s | [3]VC.*

Here lies Ursicinus, the exorcist, commemorated by the pious Laurentia.

heartfelt words memorialising loved ones warrant concerted study, inviting empathy for the profound and overwhelming grief of parents, spouses, and friends. Alongside magistrates, we encounter a promising and educated young clerk. An exorcist emerges in a city that embraces pagan sanctuaries, including the temple of Mithras and several basilicas. This paints a reliable testament to the rich tapestry of personalities in a city bridging East and West.

An in-depth analysis of specific inscriptions, chosen as representative examples, illustrates how even a single sentence can yield a wealth of information and open numerous avenues for exploration. Even from a modest corpus of, at times, uniform and formulaic inscriptions, meaningful insights can be drawn, providing glimpses into the lives of ordinary individuals. Examining small-scale interactions and experiences provides a more intimate understanding of the past. Special attention should be given to institutions with a significant impact on human behaviour and emotions, such as family, law, religion, the military, and the state.

We believe that using inscriptions as sources to analyse how societal norms, religious beliefs, or political events affected the lives and emotional experiences of specific individuals or communities would yield fruitful results in interdisciplinary comparative studies. It's crucial to recognise that, irrespective of historical context and time span, we are dealing with individuals and their lives. Avoiding generalisations sourced from material across the entire empire, we advocate adopting a microhistorical perspective, starting with individuals within the community. By placing and observing communities alongside each other, revisiting existing material, and examining details overshadowed by significant historical moments, we can unveil the genuine pattern and image of all integral parts of the Empire. The potential for crafting detailed chronicles of cities and their citizens awaits through comprehensive and interconnected examination of richer corpora, whether in terms of volume or diversity of inscriptions.

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